

Use of robust norming to create a sensitive cognitive summary score in *de novo* Parkinson's disease

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BACKGROUND / RATIONALE

► Long-term cognitive impairment is common in Parkinson's disease (PD), dementia can affect 80% of patients. Mild cognitive impairment (MCI) is also common in *de novo* disease.

► The ability to track cognitive changes, including in short-term randomized controlled trials (RCTs), is hampered by consensus concerning neuropsychological test usage and utilization of results.

► Computerized cognitive batteries and smartphone-based apps are used in PD, but most are not validated for clinical research. Global screening instruments (e.g., MMSE and MoCA), are brief, but may not be sensitive to mild short-term changes or may have significant variability. Many individual paper-and-pencil cognitive batteries are used however, it remains unclear how to best utilize and interpret results containing multiple individual (sub)scores from differently-scaled and -normed tests.

► Creating a cognitive summary score (CSS) allows for the combination of detailed neuropsychological testing with the simplicity of a single test score. In the Parkinson Associated Risk Syndrome (PARS) study, a CSS was generated from a cognitive battery and used to document subtle cognitive changes in prodromal PD. It is possible that a CSS would allow neurobiological predictors of cognitive decline to be identified and serve as an outcome measure for RCTs.

► The Parkinson's Progression Markers Initiative (PPMI) study originally had a PD-MCI Level I battery with published norms. We implemented robust norming to detect cognitive differences in PD compared with healthy controls (HCs). We hypothesized that using robust norming would increase sensitivity and adjust scores to the slight impairment reported in literature (6), and that a CSS would be more sensitive than individual test results in detecting cognitive differences in *de novo* PD patients.

STUDY DESIGN

► **Participants:** The PPMI study/cohort has been extensively described (23)(24). Inclusion criteria included: (1) asymmetric resting tremor or asymmetric bradykinesia, or at least two symptoms out of resting tremor, bradykinesia, and rigidity; (2) recent clinical diagnosis (mean [SD] duration from diagnosis = 8.5 [7.3] months); (3) untreated with PD medications; (4) dopaminergic deficit based on DAT SPECT imaging; and (5) being non-demented. HCs were required to (1) not have neurological dysfunction, (2) not have a first-degree relative with PD and (3) have a MoCA score ≥ 27 . Participants enrolled as HCs who had evidence of α -synuclein seed amplification assay (SAA) positivity were not considered as HCs.

► **Creating database:** Baseline data were used. The original cognitive battery was used to create the CSS to optimize data available. This original battery was composed of the Hopkins Verbal Learning Test-Revised (HVLt-R immediate and delayed free recall scores)(24), the Benton Judgment of Line Orientation - 15 item version (JLO)(25), Symbol-Digit Modalities Test (SDMT)(26), Letter-Number Sequencing (LNS)(27), and semantic (animal) fluency(28).

► **Published norms:** Using previously published methods derived from participants not enrolled in PPMI, "external" standard scores were derived. This included T-scores for the HVLt-R (immediate and delayed free recall scores), SDMT and semantic fluency, and scaled scores for the JLO and LNS.

► **Robust norming:** The robust HC group was defined using the criteria depicted in Figure 1. Participants were required to have a baseline MoCA of ≥ 27 , a year 1 MoCA score of ≥ 26 , and not have had more than a 2-point drop in their MoCA score between baseline and year 1. This subset of participants was used to create internal norms for each test which were then used to calculate internally-derived z-scores for each participant (see Statistical Analysis for details).

STUDY DESIGN (CONT'D)

► **Analyses:** Statistical analyses were performed using SAS v9.4 (SAS Institute Inc., Cary, NC; sas.com; RRID:SCR_008567). Statistical analysis codes used to perform the analyses in this article are shared on Zenodo [10.5281/zenodo.12636045].

► All external standard scores derived from published norms were converted to z-scores and then capped at -3 to 3. To derive internal norms, the robust HC population was used to build a linear regression model for each test. Age, sex, and continuous education were considered as predictors of raw test scores. The second order polynomials of centered age and education were also considered. Sex was coded as a binomial variable with male = 1 and female = 2. Backwards selection with a cutoff of alpha = 0.10 was used to determine which variables would appear in each final model. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was used to assess the normality of the residuals of each model. These derived linear models were used to calculate an "expected" raw score for each participant and each test, and a z-score was calculated by taking the participant's raw score minus their expected score and dividing by the root mean square error. These internal norms were also capped at -3 to 3.

► Two cognitive summary scores were calculated for each participant, one being an average of their six external z-scores (derived from published norms), and the other an average of their six internal z-scores (derived from the PPMI robust HC subgroup), with the six z-scores weighted equally.

► For each variable in Table 1, two-sample t-tests and chi-squared tests were performed to compare the PD group to each of the HC groups. Cohen's d effect sizes were used to compare these composite scores across groups.

RESULTS

Table 1. Demographic characteristics of PD and HC cohorts

Variable	PD group		HC group		p-values	
	All <i>de novo</i> PD (N = 923)	All HC (N = 250)	Robust HC (N = 154)	PD vs. All HC	PD vs. Robust HC	
Age at baseline , mean (SD)	63.1 (9.4)	61.2 (11.6)	59.1 (11.6)	0.0077	<0.001	
Median (min, max)	63.6 (33.5, 84.9)	62.8 (30.4, 85.3)	60.5 (30.6, 85.3)			
Sex , n (%)						
Male	607 (65.8%)	154 (61.6%)	94 (61.0%)	0.2212	0.2548	
Female	316 (34.2%)	96 (38.4%)	60 (39.0%)			
Education , mean (SD)	16.0 (3.1)	16.1 (3.1)	16.1 (3.0)	0.7029	0.8769	
Median (min, max)	16 (5, 32)	16 (6, 24)	16 (8, 24)			
Race , n (%)						
White	856 (93.3%)	221 (88.8%)	140 (91.5%)	0.0155	0.4051	
Black or African American	18 (2.0%)	16 (6.4%)	8 (5.2%)			
Asian	14 (1.5%)	5 (2.0%)	2 (1.3%)			
Other	29 (3.2%)	7 (2.8%)	3 (2.0%)			
Ethnicity (Hispanic or Latino) , n (%)	32 (3.5%)	4 (1.6%)	2 (1.3%)	0.1288	0.1523	
Months since PD diagnosis , mean (SD)	8.5 (7.3)	N/A	N/A	—	—	
Median (min, max)	5.9 (0.4, 42.8)	N/A	N/A			
MDS-UPDRS Part III , mean (SD)	22.4 (9.7)	1.3 (2.1)	1.1 (1.8)	<.0001	<.0001	
Median (min, max)	21 (3, 62)	0 (0, 13)	0 (0, 10)			
MoCA , mean (SD)	26.9 (2.4)	28.0 (1.5)	28.3 (1.1)	<.0001	<.0001	
Median (min, max)	27 (15, 30)	28 (20, 30)	28 (27, 30)			
HVLt-R Immediate Recall , mean (SD)	24.3 (5.1)	25.8 (4.7)	27.0 (4.4)	<.0001	<.0001	
Median (min, max)	24 (9, 36)	26 (13, 36)	27.5 (14, 36)			
HVLt-R Delayed Recall , mean (SD)	8.3 (2.7)	9.2 (2.4)	9.7 (2.2)	<.0001	<.0001	
Median (min, max)	9 (0, 12)	10 (2, 12)	10 (3, 12)			
Judgment of Line Orientation , mean (SD)	12.8 (2.2)	13.1 (2.1)	13.3 (1.9)	0.0243	0.0079	
Median (min, max)	13 (1, 15)	14 (2, 15)	14 (4, 15)			
Letter Number Sequencing , mean (SD)	10.5 (2.7)	10.9 (2.7)	11.3 (2.8)	0.0607	0.0009	
Median (min, max)	11 (2, 20)	11 (2, 20)	11 (2, 20)			
Semantic Fluency (Animals) , mean (SD)	21.2 (5.3)	21.9 (5.4)	22.6 (5.5)	0.0470	0.0018	
Median (min, max)	21 (7, 41)	21.5 (10, 38)	22 (10, 38)			
Symbol Digit Modalities Test , mean (SD)	41.9 (10.3)	47.3 (10.3)	48.8 (10.5)	<.0001	<.0001	
Median (min, max)	42 (7, 82)	47 (20, 83)	48 (20, 83)			

RESULTS

Table 2. Published norms z-scores at baseline among *de novo* PD and HC cohorts

Variable	PD Group	HC Group		Cohen's d*	
	All <i>de novo</i> PD (N = 923)	All HC (N = 250)	Robust HC (N = 154)	PD vs All HC	PD vs Robust HC
HVLt-R Immediate Recall , mean (SD)	-0.42 (1.09)	-0.12 (1.04)	0.08 (1.02)	-0.28	-0.47
Median (min, max)	-0.40 (-3.00, 2.40)	0.00 (-3.00, 2.40)	0.10 (-3.00, 2.40)		
HVLt-R Delayed Recall , mean (SD)	-0.50 (1.18)	-0.10 (1.09)	0.06 (1.01)	-0.34	-0.48
Median (min, max)	-0.30 (-3.00, 3.00)	0.20 (-3.00, 1.40)	0.35 (-3.00, 1.40)		
Judgment of Line Orientation , mean (SD)	0.65 (0.99)	0.83 (0.94)	0.89 (0.90)	-0.18	-0.25
Median (min, max)	0.80 (-2.81, 2.49)	0.95 (-2.21, 2.57)	1.03 (-2.21, 2.57)		
Letter Number Sequencing , mean (SD)	0.52 (0.94)	0.61 (0.93)	0.71 (0.96)	-0.10	-0.20
Median (min, max)	0.67 (-2.67, 3.00)	0.67 (-2.67, 3.00)	0.67 (-2.67, 3.00)		
Semantic Fluency (Animals) , mean (SD)	0.10 (1.00)	0.17 (1.10)	0.25 (1.11)	-0.07	-0.14
Median (min, max)	0.10 (-3.00, 3.00)	0.10 (-2.80, 3.00)	0.20 (-2.60, 3.00)		
Symbol Digit Modalities Test , mean (SD)	-0.40 (0.98)	0.08 (1.02)	0.19 (1.03)	-0.49	-0.60
Median (min, max)	-0.38 (-3.00, 3.00)	0.00 (-2.75, 2.90)	0.11 (-2.38, 2.90)		

Table 3. Internally-derived, regression-based z-scores at baseline among *de novo* PD and HC cohorts

Variable	PD Group	HC Group		Cohen's d*	
	All <i>de novo</i> PD (N = 923)	All HC (N = 250)	Robust HC (N = 154)	PD vs All HC	PD vs Robust HC
HVLt-R Immediate Recall , mean (SD)	-0.56 (1.11)	-0.25 (1.04)	0.00 (0.99)	-0.29	-0.52
Median (min, max)	-0.52 (-3.00, 2.21)	-0.18 (-3.00, 2.37)	0.06 (-2.88, 2.37)		
HVLt-R Delayed Recall , mean (SD)	-0.54 (1.14)	-0.17 (1.07)	0.00 (0.99)	-0.32	-0.48
Median (min, max)	-0.33 (-3.00, 1.56)	0.03 (-3.00, 1.61)	0.18 (-3.00, 1.61)		
Judgment of Line Orientation , mean (SD)	-0.24 (1.07)	-0.04 (1.01)	0.01 (0.95)	-0.18	-0.23
Median (min, max)	-0.03 (-3.00, 1.80)	0.18 (-3.00, 2.02)	0.19 (-3.00, 2.02)		
Letter Number Sequencing , mean (SD)	-0.22 (0.95)	-0.12 (0.94)	0.00 (0.99)	-0.10	-0.22
Median (min, max)	-0.20 (-3.00, 3.00)	-0.15 (-2.85, 3.00)	-0.10 (-2.85, 3.00)		
Semantic Fluency (Animals) , mean (SD)	-0.25 (0.96)	-0.12 (0.98)	0.00 (1.00)	-0.13	-0.26
Median (min, max)	-0.36 (-3.00, 3.00)	-0.18 (-2.31, 2.73)	-0.12 (-2.31, 2.73)		
Symbol Digit Modalities Test , mean (SD)	-0.56 (1.01)	-0.07 (0.98)	0.00 (0.98)	-0.49	-0.55
Median (min, max)	-0.56 (-3.00, 3.00)	-0.05 (-2.46, 3.00)	-0.04 (-2.46, 3.00)		

Table 4. Cognitive summary score using published and internally-derived norms

Variable	PD Group	HC Group		Cohen's d*	
	All <i>de novo</i> PD (N = 923)	All HC (N = 250)	Robust HC (N = 154)	PD vs All HC	PD vs Robust HC
Published norms					
CSS, mean (SD)	-0.01 (0.64)	0.25 (0.61)	0.36 (0.61)	-0.42	-0.59
Median (min, max)	0.02 (-2.34, 1.99)	0.26 (-1.73, 1.99)	0.32 (-1.73, 1.99)		
Internally-derived norms					
CSS, mean (SD)	-0.40 (0.68)	-0.12 (0.62)	0.00 (0.61)	-0.41	-0.60
Median (min, max)	-0.34 (-2.75, 1.76)	-0.12 (-1.85, 1.83)	-0.03 (-1.85, 1.83)		

CONCLUSIONS

► PD patients perform worse cognitively than HC at disease diagnosis on multiple cognitive domains, particularly information processing speed and verbal memory.

► Using robust norming increases effect sizes and lowers the scores of PD patients to "expected" levels.

► The CSS performed better than all individual cognitive tests.

Robust norming enhanced sensitivity in detecting cognitive differences in *de novo*, untreated PD, and generated scores consistent with the mild cognitive deficits known to commonly occur in prodromal and early disease. The CSS generated after the robust norming process combines the richness of a detailed, multi-domain cognitive battery with the simplicity a single, identically-normed and equally-weighted score with potential for domain subscores. A CSS developed using a robust norming process may be sensitive to cognitive changes in the earliest stages of PD and have utility as an outcome measure in clinical research, including clinical trials.

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PPMI data downloaded from PPMI website: <http://www.ppmi-info.org/>

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